

An updated high-resolution, site-specific *Karenia brevis* bloom severity index and associated respiratory irritation impacting the southwest Florida coast

Fig. 1. Study area and location in Florida (inset), showing Florida Wildlife Research Institute (FWRI) cell sample locations (red circles). The yellow squares indicate the eight Beach Conditions Reporting System (BCRS) beach sites in Manatee and Sarasota Counties that are monitored by the Mote Marine Lab.

Recurring “red tides” along the coast of southwest Florida, caused by the toxic dinoflagellate *Karenia brevis*, typically begin in late summer or fall. They can persist for months to over a year, and extend from tens to hundreds of kilometers along the shoreline [1–2]. These blooms are problematic because *K. brevis* produces brevetoxins (BTX)—potent neurotoxins that accumulate in shellfish. The resulting risk of neurotoxic shellfish poisoning (NSP) triggers widespread closures of shellfish beds to

protect consumers. Additionally, when *K. brevis* cells rupture, BTXs become aerosolized through wave breaking or wind-driven turbulence [3–4]. Exposure to aerosolized BTXs causes respiratory irritation or illness in beachgoers and increased emergency room visits [5]. As a result, both residents and tourists often avoid beaches when red tides are reported [6], causing significant economic losses to local businesses [7]. Severe blooms can also cause fish kills and mass mortalities of endangered

manatees, bottlenose dolphins, sea turtles, and seabirds [8].

Although the public often perceives blooms as affecting the entire west coast of Florida, they are typically patchy and shift with oceanic currents. Capturing these spatial and temporal variations is essential for developing accurate location-specific bloom severity indices. In 2022, our group developed the first fine-scale indices for *K. brevis* bloom intensity and associated respiratory irritation for southwest Florida [9]. The Bloom Severity Index (BSI) was based on *K. brevis* cell concentrations collected by the Florida Fish and Wildlife Conservation Commission (FWC) from 1953–2019. The concentrations were binned by month into 0.2° latitudinal sections along the shoreline, and the frequency with which threshold concentrations were exceeded in each bin across the region was calculated for each month or each year to give a severity estimate [9]. A normalized BSI was defined from 0–10, with 10 representing the most severe bloom and 0 representing absence. Because the BSI reflects both spatial and temporal extent, it is a valuable dataset for assessing site-specific severity and validating future bloom models [9].

To quantify respiratory impacts, a corresponding Respiratory Irritation Index (RI) was developed for 2006–2019 using Beach Condition Reporting System (BCRS) data from Mote Marine Laboratory. Volunteers routinely reported respiratory irritation at six Sarasota County beach sites (2006–2025) and two in Manatee County (since 2007) (Fig. 1). Reports include time, location, and respiratory irritation severity measure determined by the frequency of coughs and sneezes heard over 30-second intervals. The resulting respiratory measures were categorized as producing no, slight, moderate, or high (severe) respiratory irritation. The monthly and annual RIs were then quantified as percentage of beach days during each month where respiratory problems were reported. Similar to the BSI, a normalized 10-point RI scale was

Fig. 2. (A). Hovmöller (time-latitude) diagram for the 0.15-degree latitude-binned monthly-maxima of observed *K. brevis* cell counts within 5 km (3 mile) polygon (as shown in Fig. 1) from 1953 to early 2024. (B). The Bloom Severity Index (BSI) for southwest Florida [25.4°–28.4° N], represent the relative number of “bin-months” normalized to a maximum value of ten. For each bin, the maximal cell count was determined and classified into five categories: <math><5,000</math> (light gray), $>5,000$ $>50,000$ $>100,000$ and $>1,000,000$ cells L^{-1} (salmon color to dark red). White in (A) indicates no samples were taken. In (B), black crosses on the x-axis indicate months with no cell observations in the entire region, and gray circles indicate months where samples were available but no blooms were observed. See [9] for binning methods.

Fig. 3. Annual Bloom Severity Index (BSI, July to next June) for (A). the Southwest Florida coast ranging from Collier to Pinellas Counties (see Figure 1), (B). Pinellas County, (C). Manatee and Sarasota Counties, (D). Lee and Charlotte Counties and (E) Collier County. Some counties were combined because of their shorter shorelines compared to others. The BSI for each county was derived using the same approach as in (A), except that they were normalized by the total number of 0.15-degree latitudinal bins for that county. Black crosses indicate no samples taken, and gray circles indicate samples with no blooms observed.

developed, with 10 representing the highest number of beach days and 0 representing the lowest.

Over the past two decades, the quantity and frequency of sampling of *K. brevis* densities along the southwest Florida shoreline has progressively increased, owing to significant efforts coordinated by the FWC. To take advantage of this higher-resolution dataset, we reanalyzed the historical data by partitioning it into smaller 0.15° latitude bins by month and adding the five recent years of data [9]. The dataset now spans from 1953 through 2024, ending with the 2023 bloom year (defined as July–June of the following year,

since blooms typically begin in the latter half of the year). This analysis only included data collected within ~4.8 km of the coast (Fig. 1), where cell counts are most consistently available. As before, each monthly bin was examined to determine whether the maximum cell count exceeded any of five categories (Fig. 2A; see caption for details), and severity indices were calculated. The five categories were defined as follows. Below 5,000 cells L⁻¹ is considered safe and >5,000 cells L⁻¹ is the threshold above which shellfish beds may be closed. The other thresholds, low, medium and high, are based on potential risk categories used by FWC. The low

category, >50,000 cells L⁻¹, indicates when individuals most sensitive to respiratory irritation begin to experience symptoms [9]. The medium category, >100,000 cells L⁻¹, designates when all beachgoers have an increased likelihood of experiencing respiratory irritation. A high concentration, >1,000,000 cells L⁻¹, represent a probable risk of discomfort and adverse health effects. Revised severity indices were calculated using the binned data for these five categories. To assess respiratory impacts, we also extended the RI from our previous work [9] to January 2025 based on the updated BCRS data.

Bloom Severity Index (BSI). Compar-

Fig. 4. (A). The monthly Respiratory Irritation (RI) index for the eight Beach Condition Reporting System (BCRS) stations in Sarasota and Manatee Counties, FL, was derived from data collected from August 2006 to January 2025. Black crosses represent months with no available BCRS data reported, and gray circles indicate months with no reported respiratory irritation. (B). The accumulated RI was calculated for each bloom year (from August to July of the following year). The 2024 RI index includes data only from August 2024 to January 2025. (C). The Annual BSI for Sarasota and Manatee Counties. In all panels, black crosses indicate months with no cell observations or respiratory irritation reports available for the two counties, while gray circles indicate months where samples were available but no blooms were observed.

Table 1. The percent of the time when *Karenia brevis* cell concentrations >5,000, >50,000, or >100,000 cells L⁻¹ were observed in a given 0.15° latitude bin, that increasingly higher cell concentrations would also be present at the same location during the same monthly time period.

<i>K. brevis</i> cells L ⁻¹	>5,000	>50,000	>100,000	>1,000,000
>5,000	-	71%	61%	24%
>50,000	-	-	86%	34%
>100,000	-	-	-	39%

ing the updated Hovmöller diagram with our previous version shows that the current 0.15° bin resolution dataset (previously 0.20° latitudinal bins), provides finer spatial detail along the coast with fewer gaps (Fig. 2A–B). The normalized monthly BSI along southwest Florida shoreline was almost identical to Stumpf et al. (2022) [9], though minor differences exist (Fig. 2A). Notably, the March 2023 bloom in this updated index replaced the previously February 2016 [8], as the highest BSI score of 10, reflecting the most extensive bloom of >5,000 cells L⁻¹ (Fig. 2B). The months with the widest extent of more intense bloom concentrations can also be identified; for instance, August 2018 exhibited the broadest bloom at concentrations > 10⁶ cells L⁻¹ (BSI = 7.1). (Note that the 2023 dataset is provisional and may undergo minor revisions after quality control.)

Interannual variability of K. brevis blooms in southwest Florida and individual counties. For the area from Pinellas to Collier counties, the highest BSI at 5,000 cells L⁻¹ occurred in bloom year 2002 (Fig. 3A) (Pasco and Hernando counties were excluded in this analysis due to inconsistent sampling; Fig. 2A). During 2002, although the bloom was continuous in space and time (Fig. 2A), it was not sufficiently intense to rank among the most severe bloom years. Examination of the bloom concentrations >100,000 cells L⁻¹ threshold showed that years such as 2001, 2006, 2012, 2018, and 2022 recorded higher BSIs. The 2020 bloom persisted into 2021, producing an intense summer bloom that year. Similarly, the 2017 bloom extended into 2018, culminating in a severe bloom in the summer of 2018 with a maximum BSI at >10⁶ cells L⁻¹ in July. Over the past three decades, two bloom years stand out for their absence of blooms: 2010, when *K. brevis*

was not detected along the southwest Florida coast, and 2023, when only a few samples recorded low cell counts. This stands in stark contrast to the comparatively severe blooms observed in several intermediate years, i.e., 2012, 2016, 2018, 2020, and 2022 (Fig 2B).

The high-resolution bins also allow for detailed analysis of blooms in individual counties (Fig. 3B–E), providing insight into when site-specific blooms occurred and how individual counties contributed to overall bloom severity. For example, the 1957 bloom was widespread (>5,000 cells L⁻¹) across all counties, but severe blooms (>1,000,000 cells L⁻¹) were primarily confined to Pinellas County. Another example is from 2007 to 2014, and in 2019, when

blooms were not recorded in Pinellas, but did occur in the other counties, confirming the spatially patchy nature of the blooms. Additionally, in 2022 other counties experienced much more intense blooms than in 2021, whereas in Pinellas the 2021 bloom was stronger than that of 2022.

Respiratory irritation impact (RI) index for Sarasota and Manatee Counties. The RI index (Fig. 4A) was defined by the number of beach days for each respiratory irritation condition (present or slight, moderate, and high or severe, respectively) and normalized to the month/year with the most beach days. The monthly RI shows that the most severe respiratory irritation occurred in winter 2018. Moderate RI levels were recorded in summer–fall 2021, fall 2022–spring 2023, and fall–winter 2006/2016. The annual RI index (Fig. 4B) reached its maximum in the bloom year 2018 (10), followed by 2022 (5.9), and 2016 (5.6). In contrast, the RIs in 2007–2011, 2013–2014, and 2023 were almost negligible (< 1), while the 2010 bloom season (a bloom-free year) showed no reported respiratory irritation.

Fig. 5. This graph shows the relationship between the annual, bloom year, Respiratory Irritation impact (RI) index and the annual Bloom Severity Index (BSI). Many years showed negligible BSI or RI (2007, 2008, 2010, 2014, and 2023), or only slight blooms (2009, 2013, and 2011). Colors indicate onshore wind frequency, obtained from the National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration VENN1 wind station, at Venice, Sarasota County) from November of each year through next February, with gray squares indicating years with no wind observations. Circle size represents the average wind speed for each year. The black dashed line shows the linear regression between the two indices.

Coherence between BSI and RI. The coherence between the BSI and RI was previously examined [8]. The results showed that, at the monthly scale, *K. brevis* blooms and associated respiratory irritation were correlated, with RI values increasing during more intense blooms. However, because earlier BSI analyses were conducted across the entire southwest Florida region, they were not site- or county-specific. This may have introduced spatial aliasing between bloom observations and reports of irritation impacts. In this study, we narrowed the BSI and RI analysis to Sarasota and Manatee counties (Fig. 4), which have the longest and most complete datasets. We plan to provide annual updates of the indices by county. For simplicity, the present analysis focused on interannual timescales, where the two indices show coherent variability. This allowed us to examine the RI compared to different severity thresholds (Fig. 4). In general, blooms exceeding $>50,000$ cells L^{-1} are associated with mild to moderate respiratory irritation impacts [10]. At the county level, the previously reported relationship between BSI and RI [9] remains valid (Fig. 5). A linear relationship exists between BSI and RI, but it is influenced by variability in onshore wind frequency (Fig. 5). More frequent onshore winds substantially increase the RI relative to BSI, as seen in 2018. Less frequent onshore winds (2006, 2015) result in a lower RI compared to BSI. An exception occurred in 2012, when RI was lower than expected despite frequent onshore winds, likely due to relatively low wind speeds in 2012 (Fig. 5). These results confirmed that: (1) County-specific BSI and RI are well correlated; (2) Irritation impact was only observed when blooms exceeded $50,000$ cells L^{-1} ; (3) Increased onshore wind frequency augmented irritation impact in most years.

Are low K. brevis cell concentrations ($>5,000$ cells L^{-1}) predictive of the occurrence of high-density blooms that can cause respiratory irritation? The analysis revealed that when $>5,000$ cells L^{-1} occur in a given 0.15° latitude bin, there is a 71% probability that $>50,000$ cells L^{-1} would also be observed during the same month (Table 1). In addition, 61% of these events were accompanied by blooms of $> 100,000$ cells L^{-1} . This sug-

gests that the presence of a low concentration bloom ($>5,000$ cells L^{-1}) in a given location, is often an indicator of bloom densities sufficient to cause mild to moderate respiratory irritation. In contrast, only 24% of the time did concentrations of $>1,000,000$ cells L^{-1} occur in the same bin where $>5,000$ cells L^{-1} had been recorded. Thus, the most intense blooms are not readily predictable based solely on the detection of lower-density blooms.

The methods used in this study can be updated annually to help managers estimate the likelihood of local communities being affected by blooms once low cell concentrations are detected. They also provide an overall probability of bloom impacts at the community level, aiding in contingency planning. This binning strategy may also prove useful in other regions where routine monitoring is conducted.

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Authors

Yizhen Li & R Wayne Litaker, CSS Inc. Under Contract to National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration, National Ocean Service, National Centers for Coastal Ocean Science, Silver Spring, MD, USA

Richard Stumpf, National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration, National Ocean Service, National Centers for Coastal Ocean Science, Silver Spring, MD, USA

Barbara Kirkpatrick, Gulf of America Coastal Ocean Observing System Regional Association, Department of Oceanography, College Station, TX, USA

Katherine Hubbard, Fish and Wildlife Research Institute, Florida Fish and Wildlife Conservation Commission, St. Petersburg, FL, USA

Katherine Kohler Harrison, Gulf of America Alliance, Ocean Springs, MS, USA

Email corresponding author:
Yizhen.Li@noaa.gov

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